

KEY ISSUES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ACCOUNTING POLICY IN NON-GOVERNMENT EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *The article highlights the importance of accounting policy and current issues in its development. In particular, based on the characteristics of the activities of non-governmental educational organizations, the different aspects of the development of accounting policy in accounting in enterprises of this branch are highlighted.*

Key words: *accounting policy, non-governmental educational organizations, accounting, financial reporting, international standards of financial reporting.*

The changes taking place in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a number of adopted normative documents are being implemented in various sectors, and today, measures are being developed to transfer accounting carried out by enterprises and organizations to international standards. In particular, the adopted "Regarding the additional measures of transition to international standards of financial reporting"¹. The task of conducting accounting on the basis of international standards of financial reporting defined in the normative legal document is one of the most pressing issues today. The implementation of the tasks specified in these regulatory documents directly depends on the correct organization and management of accounting in enterprises and organizations. This, in turn, is the organization of the educational process in the enterprises of this sector, the correct management of expenses, the determination and reduction of the cost of educational services, the recognition of income based on best practices, includes the most basic tasks of accounting, such as reflecting these processes in accounting and financial reporting forms based on international standards of financial reporting.

These tasks are solved differently in enterprises and organizations and are reflected in their accounting policies. Today, in the development of accounting policies in non-governmental educational organizations, the development of methodological procedures for the correct organization of educational services processes, the correct allocation of direct and indirect costs to the cost of educational services, and their transparent reflection in the forms of accounting and financial reporting are urgent tasks. Solving these tasks in non-state educational organizations directly depends on the accounting policy of organizations, and this process is of particular importance in the organization of accounting in economic entities. As a result of the research, it became clear that the accounting policy has become important in the organization and management of accounting in enterprises and organizations based on their activity processes, and the accounting policy as an economic category required the definition and description of economists, and the research of scientific research: "Accounting policy is a set of principles and procedures adopted by the head of the enterprise for accounting and financial reporting"². The accounting policy reflects not only the rules of accounting and reporting, but also the directions of accounting organization based on the characteristics of business entities, the procedures for compiling and

¹ Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures for the transition to international standards of financial reporting". February 24, 2020. PQ-4611.

² Urazov K.B., Polatov M.E. Accounting. Textbook. - T.: "Science and Technology Publishing House" - 2021, 560 pages.

presenting reports that meet the requirements of management information users. Therefore, this definition does not fully cover all accounting and reporting areas that should be covered in the accounting policy.

In the course of research, normative legal documents, in particular the definitions given in national and international standards, were studied. "Accounting policy and financial reporting" in the national accounting standard No. 1 "Accounting policy means a set of methods adopted by the head of an economic entity for accounting and financial reporting, financial reporting is prepared in accordance with these methods and in accordance with their rules and principles" is defined³.

"Accounting Policy, Changes and Errors in Accounting Estimates" is defined in the international financial reporting standard of International Accounting Standards (IAS) No. 8 as follows: "Accounting policy is the specific principles, methods, customs, rules used by a business entity in the preparation and presentation of financial statements and practice"⁴.

From these definitions given in national and international standards, it can be concluded that the main purpose of this document developed by enterprises and organizations is to assist in the preparation of financial reporting forms.

Although the activities of enterprises and organizations are not taken into account separately in the preparation of the accounting policy in accordance with the requirements of the international accounting doctrine, but different from our national standards, in financial reporting applications, enterprises and organizations should cover and present information in a way that meets the needs of internal and external information users based on their activity characteristics.

Such procedures presented in international standards help to improve the accounting policy in enterprises, especially in non-governmental educational organizations, to increase the level of usefulness of financial reporting forms, and to provide more complete information of financial and managerial importance. We believe that compliance with these principles in the development of accounting policy in non-governmental educational organizations will serve to increase the investment attractiveness of financial and management reports, to make correct management decisions, and to improve accounting in accordance with international standards of financial reporting.

Today, accounting policies in non-governmental educational organizations, like other types of economic entities, are developed on the basis of the national accounting standard "Accounting Policy and Financial Statements" No. 1. According to this standard, the accounting policy is developed by each organization at the beginning of the reporting year and approved by the head of the accounting service. Organizations are not allowed to make changes to the accounting policy in the middle of the year and carry out their activities in accordance with this document. Also, due to the fact that accounting processes in non-state educational organizations are carried out in specialized and automated modern accounting programs, the accounting policy is also loaded in these programs.

We believe that there is a need to improve the accounting policy developed by non-governmental educational organizations operating in our republic based on the characteristics of their service activities. This imposes on non-governmental educational organizations the task of developing an "Accounting policy for the organization and management of accounting accounts in non-governmental educational organizations" that is compatible with their service activities and fully meets the requirements of international standards of financial reporting.

³ No. 1 NAS "Accounting policy and financial reporting" // by MJ on 14.08.1998. Registered with number 474.

⁴ IAS No. 8 "Accounting policies, changes in accounting estimates and errors".

In our opinion, we believe that the accounting policy of non-governmental educational organizations should be composed of the following parts:

- * Organizational structure;
- * compositional structure;
- * staff structure;
- * accounting processes;
- * recognition and evaluation of assets;
- * recognition and assessment of expenses and income;
- * presentation of tax and financial reports.

These scientific proposals on the activities of non-governmental educational organizations help to a certain extent to organize the accounting processes correctly, to maintain the accounting of expenses and income through the international standards of financial reporting. In addition, scientific works of scientists and the procedures presented in national and international standards were researched, and the author's definitions of accounting policies were developed taking into account the activities of non-governmental educational organizations. This author's definition, developed by us, serves to improve accounting from a theoretical point of view.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

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